

THE IMPACT OF GLYCEMIC PROFILE ON OVARIAN FOLLICULOGENESIS PARAMETERS IN REPRODUCTIVE-AGED WOMEN WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Introduction: Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1D) increases the risk of menstrual irregularities, subfertility, and adverse pregnancy outcomes in reproductive-aged women. However, the specific effects of different glyceamic profiles—chronic hyperglycemia, frequent hypoglycemia, glyceamic variability, and mixed dysglycemia—on ovarian folliculogenesis remain poorly understood. This study aims to evaluate the association between various glyceamic profiles and ovarian morphofunctional parameters, including ovarian volume (OV), antral follicle count (AFC), and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), in women with long-standing T1D.

Methods: Fifty women with T1D, aged 19–38 years (disease duration ≥ 10 years), were enrolled. Glycemia was assessed using continuous glucose monitoring (FreeStyle Libre) and HbA1c. Participants were divided into four groups: Group 1 (satisfactory compensation), Group 2 (frequent hypoglycemia and high glyceamic variability), Group 3 (prolonged hyperglycemia, mean HbA1c 8.4%), and Group 4 (intermittent dysglycemia). Ovarian status was evaluated by ultrasound (OV, AFC) and serum AMH/FSH levels. Spearman's correlation (r_s) was used for statistical analysis ($p < 0.05$).

Results: In Group 1, AFC showed a strong negative correlation with glyceamic variability ($r_s = -0.82$). In Group 2, OV positively correlated with glyceamic variability ($r_s = 0.68$) and time spent in hypoglycemia ($r_s = 0.88$), with hypoglycemia time reaching 57.5%. Group 3 demonstrated only moderate ovarian changes. Group 4 exhibited the most pronounced ovarian alterations, though correlation patterns differed from other groups. No significant correlations were found between AMH/FSH and glyceamic parameters across groups.

Discussion: Both chronic hyperglycemia and recurrent hypoglycemia with high glyceamic variability significantly affect ovarian folliculogenesis. The negative

correlation between glycemic variability and AFC suggests that glucose fluctuations impair ovarian reserve even with satisfactory average glucose control. The positive correlation between OV and hypoglycemia time may indicate compensatory ovarian changes under metabolic stress. Intermittent dysglycemia caused the most severe alterations, indicating that alternating glucose extremes are particularly harmful. Traditional markers like HbA1c alone are insufficient to assess reproductive risk in T1D patients.

Conclusion: In reproductive-aged women with T1D, not only prolonged hyperglycemia but also frequent hypoglycemia and pathological glycemic variability adversely affect the ovarian follicular apparatus. The most unfavorable ovarian changes were observed in patients with frequent hypoglycemia and high glycemic variability. Preserving reproductive health in T1D women requires comprehensive glycemic management—minimizing glucose fluctuations and preventing hypoglycemia—beyond achieving target HbA1c levels.

